

International Responsibility (Definition, Pillars and Effects)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 06 , 2024</p> <p>Accepted: October 07, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : International Responsibility, Violate, Organizations</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13899707</p>	<p><i>The issue of international responsibility is one of the important and closely related topics to the issue of justice and its achievement, from redress to the victims of the affected and holding accountable the parties who violate their international obligations and trying to repair the damage by restoring the situation to what it was or resorting to material compensation. It is, therefore, necessary to know what responsibility is, its elements and implications, and with the evolution of the concept of subjects of international law to include international organizations, specialized agencies, multinational bodies and companies and even private natural individuals, the difficulty of establishing and achieving responsibility for States and international organizations does not arise as much as it arises on other legal persons and entities such as multinational corporations, bodies and private individuals. Therefore, it was necessary to address the issue of the effects of liability after verifying its verification and the mechanisms for verifying the applicability of the elements of international responsibility to the relevant legal persons. Accordingly, international responsibility was addressed in terms of concept, definition and a statement of the elements of its establishment materially, morally and internationally, and the consequent effects of repairing the damage, whether in kind, by restoring the situation to what it was or resorting to material compensation if it is not possible to restore the situation to what it was, because of its impact on reducing violations of international law and achieving security and peace in the international community.</i></p>

Introduction

International responsibility is a relatively recent topic in legal studies imposed by the rapid developments in the international community, and it continues to provoke a wide debate in international jurisprudence and action. The United Nations International Law Commission, which has been working since 1961, has not yet reached the text of an international resolution on international responsibility, and the importance of international responsibility lies in public international law as an essential part of every legal system, the effectiveness of this system depends on the maturity and growth of the rules of responsibility as a tool for development with guarantees against arbitrariness. International responsibility is the factor of ability and strength in international relations.

International jurisprudence has established that in the event of a breach of an international obligation, a new legal bond arises between two subjects of international law, namely the person in violation of the international obligation and the person injured by such a breach, and the latter has the right to claim compensation from the former. One of the most important problems of international responsibility is that it can only be held to the extent that there is damage to a person of international law.

The slightest problem arises if the injury is suffered by a State or an international organization, in which case the injury can be ascertained, which case is called direct injury. However, the problem is in proving the occurrence of damage to legal persons without those above, such as multinational companies or individuals.

We see that international law scholars differed in developing a comprehensive definition and impediment to global responsibility and in their definitions and descriptions of it as a reflection of these differences in position and trends, and through our reliance on the descriptive and analytical approach, legal articles and treaties will be addressed and their elements and their impact on reality will be analyzed.

The first topic

International responsibility: definition and elements

The importance of international responsibility lies in public international law as an essential part of every legal system, the effectiveness of which depends on the maturity and growth of the rules of responsibility as a tool of development with guarantees against arbitrariness.

The importance of standing on the meaning of international responsibility was necessary to address the definition and statement of the opinions of jurists so, and to address the pillars that are the pillar of the thing and the basis of its euphoria and resurrection, and therefore we will address this section according to the following division:

Section I: Definition of International Liability

Section II: Elements of International Responsibility

Section I

Definition of international responsibility

The definition of international responsibility idiomatically needs to determine its general meaning, as international law scholars differed in developing a comprehensive definition and an impediment to international responsibility, their definitions and descriptions of it came as a reflection of these differences in position and trends, as it was defined as (a legal system under which the State, which committed an act criminalized by international law, shall compensate for the damage caused to the aggrieved State)^[1], It has been defined as "the principle that creates an obligation to remedy any violation of international law committed by a responsible State that causes injury"^[2]

It was also defined as "the principle establishing the obligation to compensate for every breach of international law committed by a responsible State that causes injury."^[3]

It was defined as "the effect of general international law on a person's failure to respect international obligations, and international responsibility arises only between sovereign States"^[4]. It has also been defined as "a legal regime whereby a State committing an unlawful act under public international law is obliged to compensate the State that has suffered damage as a result of such an act"^[5].

The State's activity at the level of international relations within the framework of the international community raises many positions that call on the State to demand the application and respect of the provisions and rules of public international law.

Here, disagreement arises over the application or interpretation of the provisions of international law that must be respected, and the State that requests the application or interpretation of the provisions of international law and compliance with its provisions resorts to multiple methods to compel the State that violates the provisions of international law to abide by it, or to obtain compensation for the damage it suffered or to restore things to their proper status. Diplomacy to direct intervention to respect international law, whether by individual action or through collective action by international or regional organizations (for example, the UN Security Council) and in all these cases the basis of the state's action to respect international law is the international responsibility of the violating state, and thus international responsibility arises as a result of (an act contrary to an international obligation by the obligations contained in public international law by one of the subjects of public international law, causing damage to another international person, which concludes with compensation for such damages). resulting from this unlawful act)^[6]

International responsibility is defined as "international responsibility for damage suffered by others as a result of their wrongful act and compensation for it by public international law", and the provisions of international responsibility also include international organizations as subjects of international law, so the actions of organizations that would cause damage to the interests of subjects of internal law or international law entail international responsibility for those acts because it owns the act and bears the burden of responsibility.

This responsibility has been confirmed by international jurisprudence and jurisprudence, as the International Court of Justice declared in its advisory opinion issued on 13 July July 1945 the responsibility of the United Nations for the performance of contracts concluded with its officials, and the capacity of the United Nations to claim compensation from non-member States for the damage suffered by one of its officials as a result of the assassination of this official in the performance of his duties.

An international organization is responsible for any breach of a contractual obligation and for any injury to third parties, whether individual or State, noting that individuals, based on the rules of diplomatic protection, can only hold an international organization accountable through the States to which they affiliate, and lawsuits cannot be brought against international organizations before the International Court of Justice, which can only issue advisory opinions that are not binding on international organizations because, under the text of article 34 of the Statute of the Court, recourse to it is limited. Only States, and some States and international organizations resort to circumventing this provision, must agree with the State to request the advisory opinion of the Court based on the 1946 Convention on the Privileges of the United Nations, which decided that the opinions of the Advisory Court about the interpretation of this Convention shall be binding on the time.

As for the implementation of advisory opinions issued by the Court, it remains subject to the State or organization against which such advice is issued, as it is not obliged to apply them, as it may respond to them or may reject them, but a dispute in which one of the parties is an international organization can be resolved by resorting to conciliation or arbitration^[7].

There have been many intellectual trends around the definition of international responsibility.

International responsibility raises many controversial issues, and this can be attributed to several considerations, including The international obligations of the State are not precisely defined, either by international custom or based on general principles of law, in addition to the fact that the status of aliens is still disputed by many jurists.

Also, many Asian and African countries, including the Arabic States, have recently obtained their independence and entered the international community as independent and sovereign States, and these States have taken many measures to ensure their liberation at the economic and social levels, which has led foreign States whose citizens' interests have been affected by those measures to claim that international responsibility entails the obstacle of the State that carried them out, ignoring that international law cannot stand in any way as a stumbling block in the way of the economic and social emancipation of States. which has recently achieved its political liberation.

If traditional public international law, the rules of which were not shared by newly independent States, failed to understand this fact, public international law must be developed to include legal rules that are compatible with the needs of evolving international relations.

The international community has also witnessed a multiplicity of legal systems that differ among themselves, and these differences have had an impact on the position of those systems on international responsibility, at a time when the protection of individual property is the cornerstone of the capitalist system, we find that the communist system stands in an extreme position on individual property, including foreign ownership.

The topic of international responsibility is among the main areas of interest in the development of international law in the first half of the twentieth century and was chosen for codification within the framework of the League of Nations and was among the main themes of the unsuccessful conference held in The Hague in 1930, and in 1948, the United Nations General Assembly established the International Law Commission and State responsibility was chosen among the first fourteen topics to be dealt with by this new body.¹⁹⁶² The idea that the Commission should shift its focus towards defining the general rules governing the international responsibility of States was supported, and Professor Ago (Italy) as the second Special Rapporteur on the question presented eight reports and a valuable addition between 1969 and 1980. During that period, the Commission adopted 35 articles forming the basis of the articles on the origin and basic components of State responsibility, and between 1980 and 1984 Special Rapporteur Rivagn (Netherlands) introduced seven reports and his main contribution to advancing the debate reflected in the provisional adoption by the Commission of a detailed definition of an injured State.^[8]

Where we see that the definitions mentioned previously limit international responsibility to states only and this is different from what society is going through the researcher believes that this trend in the definition of international responsibility has undergone a clear change in line with international developments and developments witnessed by the international community has found people addressing the provisions of international law such as international organizations, for example, as well as the individual has sometimes become the subject of international accountability, especially about the commission of international crimes. This is noted through the judgments issued by the International Court of Justice if it considers in some of its provisions that compensation is the inevitable result of any breach in the application of any international convention, as we see in the judgment of the Permanent Court of International Justice on 13/September/1928 that according to the general concept of law, any breach of undertakings requires compensation and that this judgment came to confirm the judgment of the 1927 Shroso factory case ^[9].

After we review the previous definitions, it becomes clear to us that these definitions may differ from each other in terms of describing international responsibility, as some focus on the element of the wrongful act or act, and others focus on the element of damage and the nature of the act, without specifying at the same time the importance of the element of damage in the formation of international responsibility. This is contrary to the nature of international responsibility in its strict sense because the international community has gone through major developments that have contributed in one way or another to the development and modernization of the rules of international law to accommodate these developments. International responsibility is not only that which requires an unlawful act but can be established whenever any international person suffers injury, regardless of the nature of the act that caused the injury. ^[10].

International responsibility in its traditional form arises as a result of a different act of an international obligation committed by one of the subjects of international law causing damage, and the development of this traditional concept has hit international responsibility, as its arrangement is no longer limited to the mere commission of a violation of the legal rule, but its occurrence has become linked to the occurrence of damage resulting from an act or omission committed by an international legal person, regardless of whether this act or omission involves a violation of an international rule or not ^[11].

Section II Pillars of International Responsibility

International jurisprudence also differed on the number of elements of international responsibility, it is said that they are three (namely: the injurious act, the attribution of the act to a person of international law, and the damage)([12]), and some of them said that it is two([13]), as they limit them to the harmful act, and the attribution of the harmful act to a person of international law, and they do not consider the damage or compensation part or pillar of international responsibility. However, it can be said that the three pillars of international responsibility are necessary for damage resulting from a harmful act or a violation of an international rule or obligation, but in the case of selection of damage, international responsibility is not based on the selection of damage and the damage is not required to a certain amount or type, but the lowest damage achieves international responsibility, and material and moral damage are equal to the impact of the existence of international responsibility, there is no difference between them, and if they affect the amount of compensation, perhaps moral damage exceeds the material damage that can Limit and estimating it, unlike moral damage, which varies as much as the injured person and his status, and in this context we will address this topic according to the following division:

First: Illegal work

The act of a State is "wrongful", when it constitutes a violation of its international obligations, and the act takes this description when it involves a violation of one or more rules of general international law, whatever their source. This violation is manifested in a positive form when the State commits an act that is not legally justified, such as an attack on the border, or in its (negative) form when States refrain from doing an act required by international law. The criterion for the wrongfulness of a State's action was the rules of international law and not its internal law.

Acts carried out or refrained from by a State within the limits required for the enjoyment of its rights without arbitrariness do not entail responsibility, as the State is not held accountable, for example, for acts carried out within its territorial borders based on its right to survival and the appropriate measures it requires to ensure its security, order and respect for its legal system and its progress in various areas of its international life.

To accommodate this traditional concept, it was necessary to recognize the possibility of invoking liability by denying the wrongfulness of the act by proving the consent of the injured party, the state of legitimate defence or force majeure. All of this has led the jurisprudence of international law, having adhered to the idea of fault as a basis for responsibility,[14] to determine that the rules of traditional liability can no longer cope with the problems arising from dangerous international activities in increasing areas.[15].

In international law, responsibility is not sufficient for damage to be the result of an unlawful act, but the act must be (attributed) to the State. In all cases, the act attributable to the State shall be made by: one of its authorities or one of its nationals[16].

The Commission has taken into account the established practice of internal administrative law, in that the conduct of private individuals acting (in effect) - and in circumstances justifying it - the account of the State, is attributed to that State and entails responsibility for what is considered wrongful. For example, private individuals assume public functions after the absence of official organs during military occupation, considering that such circumstances justify the exercise of certain government functions.

The wrongful act committed by the ordinary individual on the territory of his State may be directed against a foreign (State), such as an attack on its President, funds, envoys or flag, where the responsibility of the State can arise through its general obligation to (prevent) harm to other States, and to hold accountable (suppress) its nationals who commit the wrongful act.

1- Duty to prevent: The State must prevent damage to foreign States as a result of unlawful acts by its nationals, and this duty includes taking all appropriate measures to protect some places, or some persons, if it (the State) breached this duty deliberately or negligently bore responsibility for this breach and the degree of readiness and precaution necessary to prevent damage to other States varies depending on the importance of the interest of the foreign State to be protected as well as depending on the circumstances of the occurrence of the unlawful act.

For example, when a foreign embassy is damaged by acts of sabotage, the State's liability for damage caused by private individuals against the interests of foreign States arises, with the possibility of invoking such liability based on force majeure or demonstrating the inability to prevent the damage even with the necessary measures taken to protect those interests. Responsibility for the act itself cannot be invoked in normal circumstances, where such capacity is available, and the matter is clearer in cases where it is proved that the State has encouraged or given its tacit consent to individuals to commit such an act.

2- Duty to suppress: If it refuses or neglects to prosecute and punish the person responsible for it as required by the rules of its domestic law, it bears international responsibility, on the basis that such harmful acts are related to its (passive internationally wrongful) act, which is a breach of the duty of repression to maintain or restore security and order within its territory, all of this, if the unlawful act committed by the ordinary individual on the

territory of his State is directed against foreign States or their interests. If the wrongful act is directed against foreign (private individuals) present in his State, the principle is that the responsibility that arises here is the (personal) responsibility of the wrongdoer under the rules of domestic law and before the competent national judiciary, but a breach by the State of its general obligation to prevent or suppress (may) transfer the relationship between the perpetrator of the wrongful act and the State of the injured private individual (foreign) to a relationship between the State of the perpetrator of the act, and the State of the foreign injured through what is known as (diplomatic protection).

Responsibility is based on an objective element in which the idea of fault does not play any role but is based on the fact that there is an unlawful act or act contrary to an international obligation made by the international person, regardless of the fault, if this tendency to achieve international responsibility requires a breach of an international obligation, whatever its source is a treaty, international custom or a general principle of law, and it is not required here to achieve damage resulting from this breach, but only the breach.

Some have called this theory the wrongful act and have built it on the mere causal relationship that exists between the activity of the state and the act contrary to international law, it is based on the idea of guarantee, and therefore the bad faith of the official and his fraud, i.e. deliberately harming is not a condition and does not affect the availability of responsibility or not, although it is useful in proving the attribution of the act to the international person, and good faith here lifts the legal person from international responsibility: If an international person acts in self-defence and it is proved that he committed the act in bad faith, that renders the act lawful. [17].

This theory has been taken to be broad, basing international responsibility on a guarantee for the injured regardless of the fault of the State, and is therefore incompatible with many existing situations in the international community. [18].

Therefore, international justice accepts them only in exceptional cases, such as the responsibility of a State for the acts of its non-competent officials. [19].

However, despite the criticism of risk theory, it is more suited to the true basis of international responsibility, which is to secure relations between states.

Second: Personal Element

Attribution of the wrongful act to a subject of public international law:

It is not sufficient for a subject of public international law to violate an international obligation imposed on him, whether it originates from an international treaty, a customary rule, a general principle of law, a decision of an international organization such as Security Council resolutions by Chapter VII of the Charter, or a legal rule in force at the time of the commission of the international violation for international responsibility to be incurred against him. The international act itself so that the positive or negative conduct or action (negligence contrary to an international obligation) is attributable, i.e. fixed in its right.

Attribution is a legal term whereby wrongful conduct, whether negative or positive, is attributed to the perpetrator. Subjects of public international law are legal persons who can act only through private individuals acting on their behalf or representing them. Wrongful international action is as positive as the violation of the territorial sovereignty of another State by its forces, and it may be negative.

In its draft on the codification of the rules of international responsibility, the International Law Commission has adopted this trend in Article III, which stipulates that "an international wrongful act exists when a State is attributable to conduct in a positive form or negligence by the rules of international law.²⁰ Such conduct constitutes a breach or violation of an international obligation." (The conduct of any State organ having a capacity under the domestic law of that State insofar as it appears to have acted as such shall be considered a wrongful international act under international law. This text does not raise difficulty in application and there is no difference between whether the unlawful act is attributed to bodies or authorities in the Department of International Relations such as the Head of State, the Minister of Foreign Affairs, members of the diplomatic corps or representatives of the State to organizations and between purely internal bodies. Such as the supreme authorities of the state([21]).

Third: Ordering damage to the unlawful act

Part of international jurisprudence recognized the coexistence of damage for both a wrongful act and an international responsibility, in other words, "damage should always exist until there is a wrongful act", but the first article of the International Law Commission's draft has only stated that "the responsibility of a State is held if it commits an internationally wrongful act".

The exclusion of damage from the definition of international responsibility is conceivable at the purely theoretical level, where it is possible to recognize the existence of a direct relationship between responsibility and the assault on international legality, and thus imagine how the breach occurred because of the responsibility of its perpetrator.

However, in practice, it is not possible to stand at this point in the definition of international responsibility, as this responsibility cannot be summarized and reduced only to an attack on international legality, but also

includes the existence of a new legal relationship between the perpetrator of the wrongful act and the victim State in this attack.

Attribution refers to the relationship that brings together the wrongful act with the person of public law - causation means another legal relationship, a relationship that combines the wrongful act. The injury does not create a right for the injured party to claim repair unless it is found to be the result of an unlawful act. Therefore, it is incumbent upon the injured State to prove the causal link that combines the damage caused to it with the violation committed by another State, because international law does not define his lawsuit, meaning that any person of public law can initiate a claim of responsibility against any other person who violated international legality and within the scope of international responsibility subjects of international law cannot invoke an unlawful act to establish their claim unless this act constitutes an infringement on a right protected by law, i.e. that interest in itself is not sufficient to accept their claim[22]

However, there is jurisprudence that believes that it should be limited to a legitimate interest of one of the subjects of international law, so that harm in public international law is intended to prejudice this interest, and the International Court of Justice clarified in its judgment issued in 1966 on the case of South Africa the rejection of the husband lawsuit within the scope of public international law, as it refused to give each member of the African Group the right to initiate a lawsuit to defend a public interest on the occasion of the request of Ethiopia and Liberia to rule on South Africa, and so there is no act It is internationally wrongful and therefore there is no responsibility, when there is no infringement on a right.

To say that there is a collective right to respect the law is at the same time to recognize that each subject of international law has a special right to respect the law without the need to demonstrate that it has suffered damage because of a breach of the law. It must be an individual injury to the right of a particular State so that a liability claim can be instituted. For this reason, wrongfulness that is not accompanied by damage cannot entail international responsibility. No subject of international law can demonstrate the existence of a special injury suffered individually - only international persons who can prove that injury has occurred individually can bring a claim of liability.

Moral damage is abstract and intangible and is achieved in international law in attacks on the "honour", "dignity" or sovereignty of a State, such as letting the state of demonstrators burn the flag of another country or penetrate its airspace with military aircraft. As for material damage, it is achieved by attacking the activities or funds of the injured person, whose results can be estimated economically, so that the assault constitutes the object of in-kind or financial compensation, and the judicial rulings did not differentiate between the two types of damage, so some believe that there is a scientifically similar symmetry between moral damage and legal damage and believe that unlike material damage, which is factual damage by its nature and definition, legal damage is based on an assault on a personal right of the affected State as learned from existing rules. in the international legal system.

It was argued that it was necessary to distinguish between direct and indirect harm and that direct harm was damage that was necessarily based on an unlawful act so that it was sufficient to demonstrate that such damage was linked to a causal link with the wrongful act. It therefore considers that only direct injury is invoked with which international responsibility is inferred. [23].

The second topic

Responsibility of a State for the acts of a person of international law other than a State

One of the facts observed at the level of international relations is the steady increase in the role of international organizations in international life, where their activities vary between matters of a political, economic, social or humanitarian nature. The provisions on legal responsibility have extended to international organizations, as legal persons, contrary to the view of traditional jurisprudence to limit such provisions to sovereign States. The diversity of those activities has resulted in the possibility of causing damage to the interests of subjects of national law, which require compensation, with the consequence that the organization is considered to have an objective legal personality, separate from its members, and that it is responsible for its internationally wrongful acts. Responsible for their actions within the limits of duty and therefore their behaviour is attributed to them. We will deal with this chapter by examining international organizations in the light of the draft United Nations Convention on the International Responsibility of International Organizations.

Section I

Responsibility for international organizations

The international responsibility of international organizations is fully established if wrongful conduct is attributed to them, and this responsibility is a necessary consequence of the enjoyment of legal personality by these organizations.

Some reject this responsibility or prefer to convene it for the member States of the international organization, but the regime of international responsibility of international organizations is consistent - in its general rules - with the regime on State responsibility, where it concerns customary rules and that the rules of this responsibility are mostly aimed at protecting the interests of individuals, as follows:

First: Responsibility for the actions of the organs and employees of the international organization within the framework of their functions: The responsibility of the international organization is held because of the initiatives of its legitimate organs or because of the actions attributed to its administrative and judicial facilities, and the charters establishing or special conventions of these organizations often provide for resorting to arbitration to settle disputes with member states, where the possibility of holding the international responsibility of the organizations is implicitly benefited.

Second: Responsibility in the event of non-competence of the staff of the international organization: The international responsibility of the organization in this case, is similar to the international responsibility of the state, and in this regard, the United Nations has recognized its responsibilities for acts of violence that occurred by peacekeeping forces outside military operations, but at the same time refused to compensate victims for the actions committed by peacekeeping forces for military invasions ([24]).

Third: Damage to an international person It is not enough for the responsibility of the state to issue a breach of its obligations unless this breach results in damage to others, damage is an essential pillar of the pillars of international responsibility does not envisage its existence when it fails, if the damage is available, such as a prejudice to the right of an international person or a legitimate interest according to the definition adopted by the European Union It focuses on the idea of social responsibility is a voluntary concept that does not require the enactment of laws or the development of binding regulations for companies to carry out their responsibility towards society, added to the row of supporters Salvi Mentioning the idea of a voluntary approach to corporate social responsibility International Forum of Business Leaders, where he defined social responsibility as (doing business called openness and transparency and based on ethical principles and respect for workers, society and the environment, and developed that responsibility to provide sustainable development for society in general as well as shareholders) Hence the approach of the Chambers of Industry and Commerce and the European Union in the definition of corporate social responsibility, which can be explained that it is not in the interest of these chambers to oblige companies to perform additional burdens that may weigh its shoulders and affect the performance of its activity¹.

In summary, the study concludes that the voluntary initiative for social responsibility for enterprises of a commercial nature and profit, especially companies, has formed the first basic building block, which in turn represented the ground in which the concept of corporate social responsibility grew, after which it proceeded towards regulation as a legal obligation that necessitates responsibility and above the European Union is not credible on that.

Corporate social responsibility as a legal obligation After crystallizing clearly and growing the existence of a voluntary social commitment for companies to carry out their social responsibility, a set of ideas began to creep into unions, associations and forums based on establishment Legal frameworks regulating corporate social responsibility These frameworks can be felt in the position of the World Business Council, the World Bank and other organizations and bodies that have adopted the subject of corporate social responsibility, as the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, in its position statement on corporate social responsibility, defined it It is (the continuous legal obligation by business enterprises to act ethically in achieving their economic goals through the commitment to contribute to achieving economic development and working to improve the quality of living conditions of workers and their families in addition to the local community and society as a whole) As the above definition refers to the existence of a legal obligation as well as the first obligation, which has been described as moral, as well as the nature of the obligation contained in the definition, which cannot guarantee the effectiveness unless it is of a legal nature, and on the same approach the World Bank clarified the bank that the nature of the social responsibility of the institution is (obligations imposed to contribute to sustainable economic development) through cooperation with international law workers and this is the damage in its relationship with other persons of international law has Moral damage is more severe than material damage and is equal in the field of international liability.

Section II

Responsibility of multinational corporations

Some jurists have the basis of the legal commitment to this form of corporate social responsibility in voluntary commitment, and some do not see it as anything but thinking about companies about their responsibility and duties towards the society to which they belong, while others argue that the essence of this responsibility does not go beyond just voluntary initiatives performed by these companies ([25]).

This jurisprudential trend has its supporters and supporters, whether writers or related organizations, and these organizations are led by the Chambers of Commerce and Industry, which defined corporate social responsibility (CSR)[26], "as all attempts that contribute to the volunteering of companies to achieve social moral development, and therefore social responsibility depends on self-initiatives from companies without responsibility legally binding([27])", In the same vein, the European Union has defined social responsibility (a concept whereby companies incorporate social and environmental considerations into their business and in their interaction with stakeholders voluntarily).

The International Trade Council has adopted the concept of social responsibility with a more comprehensive definition of "the set of ethical actions that a company must take towards the society in which it operates to improve the quality of life for workers, their families and society as a whole." The American Association of Administrators defined it as a corporate management commitment to responding to changing consumer expectations, and public interest in society, and continuing to make the unique contributions of business activities aimed at creating economic wealth.

Finally, in the same vein, the definition of World Organization for Standardization defined corporate social responsibility as "the activities of the enterprise to take responsibility resulting from the impact of the actions it carries out on society and the environment to make its activities consistent with the benefits of society and sustainable development."

The study concludes from the previous definitions that obligations of a non-binding ethical nature have evolved into obligations regulated by law ([28]), and then included in the work contexts adopted by the institution because companies have a direct and insignificant impact towards the society in which they exist.

From this standpoint, it was necessary to repurpose the role of companies and lead them towards the performance of their obligations to society.

The International Trade Council for Development adopted the concept of social responsibility with a more comprehensive definition of "the set of ethical actions that a company must take towards the society in which it operates to improve the quality of life for workers, their families and society as a whole", and defined by the American Administrators Association as (the commitment of corporate management to respond to changing consumer expectations, public interest in society, and continuing to make the unique contributions of business activities aimed at creating economic wealth)[29].

Finally, in the same vein, the definition of World Organization for Standardization defined corporate social responsibility as (activities of the facility to bear the responsibility resulting from the impact of the work it carries out on society and the environment to make its activities consistent with the benefits of society and sustainable development)[30].

We conclude from the previous definitions that obligations of a non-binding ethical nature have evolved to become obligations regulated by law and thus included within the work contexts adopted by the institution, because companies have a direct impact and cannot be underestimated towards society in which they exist, and from this point of view it was necessary to re-employ the role of companies and lead them towards performing their obligations to society.

The third topic

Effects of international responsibility

The traditional international jurisprudence used to deal with the effects of international responsibility in a narrow framework related to the issue of (repair) damage, although the forms of this reform differ, at a time when the development of contemporary international activities must be reflected on the rules of international responsibility in general and its effects in particular, and the most appropriate order for those effects is to include them within two segments.:

First: direct effects mainly revolve around (new obligations incurred by the State committing internationally wrongful conduct, to get it to respect previous obligations, so they are immediately enforceable, and it is not envisaged that they can be abandoned because the person who bears the obligation has no choice between performing it and leaving it).

Second: indirect effects mainly revolve around the (right) of the injured State to take measures that enable it to repair or compensate for the damage suffered, after clarifying it, and since these effects are related to the right of the injured State, it is possible to leave them, because whoever owns the right has a choice between claiming it and leaving it ([1])

First: Direct Effects of International Responsibility :

The conduct of the State that constitutes a breach of its existing obligations entails - directly - legal effects that are completely independent of any doubts or claims taken by the injured State, and aim to match (present) the relationship between the two States with the (past) of that relationship, so the first State has new obligations aimed at Getting it to (desist) from continuing to commit such behaviour, then providing the necessary assurances and guarantees after its repetition, and obliging it to lead to (restitution) or restoration of the situation in its relations with the injured State to what it was. before committing the conduct causing its responsibility. The State's obligation to desist from its internationally wrongful conduct is one of the most important effects of international responsibility and means the re-compatibility between the conduct of the designated State and the international obligation that consumed it, and this is done by cancelling or eliminating the source of the damage without going into the removal of the effects resulting from it.

Second: Indirect effects of international responsibility :

The lifting of an internationally wrongful act or reparation for the damage resulting therefrom, may not be possible or sufficient through the obligation of the responsible State to stop that act or to restore the situation to what it was before it was committed..

1. Countermeasures

The emergence of the direct effects of international responsibility depends on the State's administration of responsibility in (accepting) those effects, which may lead the injured State to seek actions or measures that would enable it to compel the responsible State to cease continuing to breach its obligations. However, measures taken by the injured State may constitute an obstacle to the main objective, which is the settlement of the dispute, since the act of a countermeasure is considered wrongful if it does not qualify as a countermeasure and its conditions are met.

2. Indemnification :

The role of compensation is to fill any gaps that may remain up to full reparation for the damage and if the payment of a sum of money is the direct meaning of compensation, but it is not the only means of reparation if it is possible for compensation (financial) to cover the entire material damage, it does not cover - usually - moral damage, where the performance of this function of compensation by another form of it, which is (satisfaction).

We will deal with this topic according to the following division:-

Subchapter I: The responsibility of the State for the actions of its nationals.

Section II: International responsibility for the actions of revolutionaries or rebels.

Subchapter III: Responsibility of the State for the Acts of its Authorities.

Section I

Responsibility of the State for the Actions of its Nationals

When there is no sufficient relationship between the perpetrator of the act in question and the State, the act cannot be based on the State and therefore its international responsibility is not held, as in the case of persons who do not act on behalf of the State, or about another State or the other.

The State is not at all responsible for the conduct of individuals, since such conduct cannot be attributed to it, and therefore individuals hold themselves responsible for the consequences of their wrongful international conduct. This rule has been confirmed by arbitration and diplomatic practice and dealt with in Article 11 of the International Law Commission's draft. The natural individual is an actual employee or by order of the State, in which case the individual is considered to be a member of the State.

In addition, there is a clear exception to the rule of non-international responsibility of a State because of the conduct of private individuals, namely, the international responsibility of a State due to the conduct of individuals, if there is a default on its part, that is, if adequate precautions are not taken to avoid accidents or to protect victims. In other words, the international responsibility of the State is based on the negligence of its powers towards the obligation to prevent or reform the conduct of individuals harmful to aliens.

Thus, the State is held accountable for the acts of private individuals if they affect the property, lives, rights of aliens and the interests of States in default before or after such acts, that is, if they do not take care or neglect to punish the perpetrator after the crime. If the state fails in this or it bears international responsibility, that is, this responsibility is not the complicity of the state with the individuals who commit the harmful act, but rather a breach of the international obligation that falls on its shoulders to take appropriate measures to prevent the occurrence of the act or search for the perpetrator, arrest him and bring him to justice according to the law in force, the responsibility is caused here by its negligence and lack of due diligence from its public authorities. Article XI of the International Law Commission's draft on the codification of the rules of international responsibility therefore stipulates that "a State shall be liable for injuries suffered by aliens as a result of the acts of individuals if its authority or officials have manifestly negligently failed to take measures to prevent or suppress such acts" [\[2\]](#).

Section II

State responsibility for the actions of revolutionaries and rebels

Military operations, whether carried out by rebels or the legitimate government, do not lead to liability for damage to property and persons, provided that they do not relate to the violation of the rules of armed conflict and the violation of the principles of humanitarian law, meaning that the military operations have not been carried out in violation of the rules of armed conflict and the principles of humanitarian law. In the case of a kinetic victory of disobedience, the victorious authority that became a legitimate government is responsible for all the actions that occurred by its men during the internal armed conflict and also for the measures taken by the defeated government authority, taking into account the damage that leads to war operations, and this is confirmed by many arbitration rulings on the basis that with the success of the rebels, they should be considered representatives of the national will, that is, legally responsibility is justified in the continuation of the state, but it is also possible This responsibility should be based on the application of the idea of risk.

In the event of the failure of the disobedience movement, the legitimate government is responsible for the actions of its work and not for the actions of the rebels, and this is confirmed by the arbitration provisions and ruled by Article 14/1 of the International Law Commission draft by saying, "The behaviour of the rebel movement that falls on the territory of the state or another part under its administration is not attributed to this state, meaning that this behaviour is not considered issued by the state, and some believe that this solution is not

fair, although it is the solution. It is preferable to arrange state responsibility based on the idea of risks because there is no authority without responsibility for the holder of this authority. ([3])

Section III

Responsibility of the State for the Acts of its Authorities

First: The responsibility of the state for the actions of the legislative authority International action has now settled that the behaviour of the legislative authority "Parliament" is an act of the state that can entail its international responsibility International responsibility results from the action or omission of the legislative authority, and responsibility for positive action exists when the legislative authority issues a law that contradicts an international obligation, and responsibility exists when refraining from work in two cases: The legislature does not pass the necessary laws to implement international obligations, and ignoring the repeal of a law is contrary to your international obligations. [4]

Second, on the other hand, it is not sufficient to confer international legitimacy on a procedure that it be applied at the same time to nationals, justifying this by the fact that the treatment of aliens is determined based on general international law and not based on domestic law, which each State can establish and amend at its discretion. The responsibility of the State is not limited to the application of laws promulgated by its legislative authority contrary to the provisions of international law but also extends to the provisions of its Constitution, which are often Making a National Constituent Assembly. ([5])

Third: The responsibility of the state for the actions of the executive authority The concept of the executive authority, entails the acts issued by it The responsibility of the state is a broad concept that differs from what is sometimes taken by domestic law, as the executive authority means the bodies and employees of the executive and administrative bodies such as the prime minister, ministers and representatives of the state. International law entails the responsibility of the state even for the actions and actions of a person or group of ordinary individuals who act in the name of the state even if they are not linked to the organs of the state any link, and this is what was adopted by the International Law Commission's draft on the codification of international responsibility in Article VIII of it, which relies on the actual link between the person who issued the act and one of the organs of the According to the aforementioned article, the reserve forces of the armed forces and the security forces that volunteer to assist the original forces, even if their services are free, their actions entail international responsibility, as well as agents sent abroad by the state to carry out acts of assassination, terrorism, sabotage and kidnapping are considered to be part of the executive power apparatus ([6]).

The concept of executive power in the field of international responsibility is a broad concept of what is taken by domestic law because it includes actual employees, and it is considered an act of the state all that is issued by regional public bodies, villages, provinces, regions, states in federal states, regardless of the administrative independence enjoyed by these entities from the state, their actions and actions are attributed to the state, and this is what was adopted by the draft International Law Commission, as it is attributed to the state and thus its international responsibility entails all acts committed. The State shall also be held accountable even if these branches are located outside the territorial boundaries of the State, as well as the State shall be held accountable for the acts of its soldiers who are on the territory of a foreign State on official mission with the consent of the latter. [7].

Hence, if a military body or forces are present on the territory of a foreign State and act as a branch or body of the sending State, the acts are attributable only to it and the host State has nothing to do with that, since its reception of such forces does not imply responsibility for the acts of each of them, as it has no control over them. A State shall be liable for the acts of private individuals if it fails in its duty to protect the property, lives and rights of aliens and the interests of other States on its territory, whether the default is before Or after these acts, that is, if they do not take due care in preventing the occurrence of the act, or if they neglect to punish the perpetrator after the crime has occurred, such as if the authorities failed to track or arrest the perpetrator, or arrested him and did not punish him, here they are responsible for the actions of individuals and must pay the necessary compensation for the damages, and this is what jurisprudence and the judiciary have settled on in international law ([8]).

The responsibility of the state for the work of the judiciary If the judiciary at home is independent of the executive authority, it is not independent of the state, but it is one of its authorities, the judgment issued by a judicial body issued by the state authorities or its branches, just like the law approved by parliament or the decision issued by the executive authority, so the opinion that the work of the judiciary does not entail the responsibility of the state because of the independence of the judiciary is outdated and unacceptable now. ([9])

Fourth: The State's Responsibility for the Work of the Judicial Authority

The domestic judiciary commits an international wrongful act in the following two scenarios:

The first hypothesis: If the judicial judgment is contrary to international obligations, the judgment issued by the internal judicial authority is contrary to the rules of international law The judiciary misinterpreted or applied an internal legal rule that is by its nature educated with the rules of international law or international obligations taken by the state upon itself, and it is also a sound interpretation or correct application The internal legal rule is inherently incompatible with the rules of international law or with international obligations that the state has

already undertaken, and the judgment is an act. It is also unlawful if the judiciary has applied an international legal rule but erred in its interpretation or application. [\[10\]](#)

Based on the foregoing, the State is internationally responsible for following a judicial ruling contrary to the provisions of international law, and this provision must meet three conditions: that the judgment involves a flagrant and unjustified violation of the provisions of domestic law, that it is issued by another court that is usually challenged in a similar manner, and that it involves a personal element of bad faith and desire between nationals and foreigners. On this basis, the enactment or survival of legislation contrary to the international obligation without application does not constitute an illegal international act that requires international responsibility, but if the law directly stipulates the rights of other countries, responsibility will ensue immediately, such as the enactment of legislation to annex part of the territory of another state, as Iraq did by issuing a decision to consider Kuwait province among the Iraqi provinces.

The second hypothesis: (denial of justice: denial of justice means any deficiency in the internal judicial organization or in the exercise of the judicial function that involves the state's breach of its international duty to judicial protection of funds and lives of foreigners) ([\[11\]](#)), and justice has been denied in the following cases: Denial of justice in its narrow sense. It means depriving foreigners in general or nationals of the plaintiff state in particular from resorting to the judiciary, or the refusal of the state courts to hear the case simply because the plaintiff is not. The judiciary is considered corrupt if the level of its organization or functioning is below the reasonable level recognized among countries, and there is a clear lack of litigation procedures or guarantees, and the court's ruling is characterized by obscene injustice as if the rulings of national courts were motivated by a spirit of xenophobia, desire and abuse of them. It is considered a denial of justice to punish an alien without a court, to fail to prosecute those responsible for a crime committed against an alien or to facilitate their escape from punishment.

We have touched in this scientific research (international responsibility - definition, pillars, effects) and we have made our effort in this research to come out in this form after we have seen several different legal sources, and after spending a long time reviewing these sources and exploring them in an accurate scientific manner we can mention some of the results and recommendations on international responsibility.

Results

1. The study of international responsibility is of particular importance in every legal system because of the guarantees it provides to ensure respect for the obligations imposed by the legal system on its persons and the consequent penalties for the violation of these obligations and non-fulfilment of them.

2 - International jurisprudence differed about the number of pillars of international responsibility, some of them said that it is three (the harmful act and the ratio of the act to a person of international law and damage) and some of them said that it is two, where they limit it to the harmful act and the ratio of the harmful act to a person of international law where they do not consider damage or compensation part or pillar of international responsibility, so it can be said that the three pillars of international responsibility for the damage resulting from the harmful act or a violation of an international rule or obligation, but in the absence of damage, international responsibility does not exist because of the absence of damage, and the damage is not required for a certain amount or type, but it is the lowest damage that achieves international responsibility.

3. The three powers of the State (the legislative authority, the judiciary, the executive or members of the State as their tools in expressing their will) are attributed to the State itself as long as the act was issued by the member by his position or by the position in which he occupies it. If the conduct of the member of the State exceeded the limits of jurisdiction established by domestic law or in contravention of the instructions received by him, it is an international practice that the conduct of the member of the State is attributable in both cases directly to the State where its international responsibility arises.

4 - The proof of international responsibility imposes on the breaching party an obligation to compensate and compensation is generally intended to make reparation for the damages arising from the commission of an act or acts contrary to international law or repair it. It is a legal term aimed at removing the damage suffered by one of the subjects of international law because of the illegal international act committed by another person.

Recommendations

1- Taking into account the principles of international responsibility as a basic rule for codifying international responsibility.

2. Researchers in this field should expand the scope of the articles on the responsibility of international organizations.

3- Contribute to the process of codifying the law of international responsibility of organizations and taking into account the responsibility of organizations for their legitimate actions that cause harm to States.

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